

ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ESL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** This article is devoted to modern strategies in teaching foreign languages and implementing it in class. Moreover, there are a lot of modern interactive activities which are widely used in teaching for ESL classes. When interactive methods are used, the student becomes a full participant in the perceiving process, and his own experience becomes the primary source of educational knowledge. The teacher does not provide ready-made knowledge, but rather encourages students to conduct their own research.*

***Keywords:** paralinguistics, praxemics, gestures, mutual, enrichment, cognition, puzzles, reference, collaborative.*

Modern education's major purpose is to develop a diverse personality capable of self-education and self-improvement. Interactive approaches and procedures are aimed at "teaching students how to learn," ensuring individualization of education, fostering independence, and supporting in the maintenance and enhancement of students' health. Interactive learning will aid in the creation of situations that will make the youngster feel accomplished. Interactive learning is defined as a process of interaction between a teacher and a student, as well as between students, in which the ability to conduct a dialogue and develop understanding between those who study and those who teach is critical. The teacher's job is to guide students' activities in order to attain the lesson's objectives. And the goal will be realized if the student participates in its formulation, because such collaborative activity will provide the student with a clear knowledge of the lesson's aims as well as a right view of the teacher's strategies for achieving the lesson's goal. Students have the right to have their own point of view on any problem, as well as the ability to share their discoveries with peers, thanks to interactive learning. The teacher should teach the students how to properly argue their points of view and to pay attention to the other participants in the discussion. The most important thing is to create a positive environment that encourages kids to engage in independent cognitive work. Thus, interactive tactics and methods assist one to defend one's side in a competent argument and provide communication skills, strong motivation, imagination, and team spirit. It may includes examples of numerous tasks, such as tests, crossword

puzzles, word puzzles, logical tasks to establish correspondence or patterns, vocabulary exercises, and project descriptions. The assignments are designed to generate universal learning activities for schoolchildren while taking into account the requirements of the second generation of educational standards. The substance of the assignments will aid in assessing the quality of students' knowledge on a regular basis [Graham, 2013].

Students will be able to qualitatively assimilate new material, evaluate their knowledge, and evaluate the knowledge of their classmates while studying a topic, and the teacher will be able to track errors on each specific topic of each individual student and rectify them. The job of the teacher in current teaching methods is to arrange the work of pupils in the classroom. This work can be done in pairs, micro groups, or big groups, according to interactive approaches and strategies (for example, work on a project). I'll go over some of the interactive approaches, forms, and work methods that I employ in my classroom. Pair work is the most basic kind of collaboration. After writing the test paper, I frequently use the form in the middle link for peer review. Such verification activity does not take much time, and it assures that both participants in the process are paying attention at all times.

Technology is defined as the science of technology, therefore learning technology is the science of learning technology. This highlights the need of using dictionaries, handouts (in the form of cards), tables (phonetic, grammatical, lexical, spelling), pictures (topic, situational, thematic), albums, maps, plans (places, buildings, rooms, etc.), a chalkboard, and other materials in the training process. At this point, teaching a foreign language without the widespread use of numerous teaching aids is impossible. The use of a sufficient variety of visual teaching aids, as well as their skillful and reasonable application, allows the teacher to engage pupils in active learning. They enable you to engage students' emotional lives, activate their mental processes (analysis, synthesis, comparison, and inference), and increase their speaking activity. If the following organizational forms of work are adopted, an increase in each student's active work time is possible: frontal, group, pair, and individual. Frontal work is recommended for teaching listening comprehension, silent reading techniques, annotating or doing other types of written work, using a dictionary or grammar reference (when all students do the same work), and using a dictionary or grammar reference (when all students do the same work). It is referred to by the teacher whenever he has to demonstrate rational work approaches to his students. On the one hand, the group work format (3-5 students per group) allows for instruction under the supervision of the group's expert. They allow you to activate students' mental processes (analysis, synthesis, comparison, and inference), as well as

improve their speaking engagement. An increase in each student's active work time is achievable if the following organizational types of work are adopted: frontal, group, pair, and individual [Hewings, 1996].

Listening comprehension, silent reading approaches, annotating or doing other sorts of written work, using a dictionary or grammar reference (where all students do the same work), and using a dictionary or grammatical reference are all advised for frontal work (when all students do the same work). When the teacher needs to illustrate rational work techniques to his students, he refers to it. On the one hand, the group work arrangement (three to five students per group) allows for more flexibility. The success of such work is determined on how well the teacher knows his students, their talents, and how effectively he can divide them into groups and identify in each one a trustworthy expert. A paired type of work should be used to teach dialogic speaking. Question-and-answer activities, training in generating dialogic units according to the model, composing dialogues according to a given circumstance, and learning dialogue can all be done in pairs. The effectiveness of this activity is determined by the teacher's attention distribution, monitoring of task completion, and providing support to those who require it. The age of students, their level of general development and language training, their level of education and degree of training, as well as the educational material and learning environments, are all determining variables in the selection of methodological methods in the educational process. As a result, teaching technology should assist in how to take into account the above aspects in order to successfully assimilate educational information and build skills and capacities in the target language. Teaching languages with a focus on communication is a good idea. The communicative method (approach) first appeared in the 1970s of the twentieth century. Its main purpose is to teach someone how to communicate, namely how to make their speech understandable to others. First and foremost, the communicative technique (approach) in language instruction is intended to educate students how to travel freely in a foreign language environment as well as how to respond appropriately in a variety of linguistic circumstances. Thus, the communicative approach of teaching entails the potential of dialogue between the student and the teacher, and is aimed at removing the student's fear of communication first and foremost, as well as maximizing the student's immersion in the language learning process. This can be accomplished by instructing a person in so-called natural settings. As a result, if we wish to educate someone to converse in a foreign language, we must do so in communicative conditions. This means that our learning should be organized in such a way that it resembles the communication process in

terms of its major traits and features. This is the essence of communication [Richards, 2013].

What is the communication process? In some partnerships, there is a need to make contact. In partnerships, the communicants' needs are recognized, and as a result, it becomes the driving force behind their actions. Perceptual communication occurs when people perceive each other visually, instinctively, or otherwise; interactive communication occurs when people interact with one other; and informational communication occurs when people exchange thoughts, ideas, interests, sentiments, or spiritual values. You can communicate in all three methods, or only one of them at a time, but this communication should be meaningful and motivated in any case. Speaking and listening, as well as paralinguistics (gestures, facial expressions) and praxemics, are used to achieve the purpose of oral communication (movement, postures). Each communicating gets new knowledge, new thoughts, new intentions, etc. as a result of the impact on each other, i.e. interprets (interprets) the acquired information. As a result, the interpretation of information is always the end outcome of communication. The communicants' relationships change as a result of interpretation, and they are once again motivated to communicate until the need is met or contact is halted for some external reason. A person's essential activity is maintained thanks to communication; without communication, human individuality would be impossible to exist [Nunan, 1987].

Interactive learning technology is a method of organizing learning events in which all participants are always engaged in active engagement. This is cooperative learning, in which the learner and the teacher are both learning subjects. It efficiently contributes to the development of skills and talents by fostering a cooperative and interactive environment. During interactive learning, students draw on their own and other people's social experiences as they work together to solve problems, resolve disagreements, discover common ground, and make compromises.

To sum up, the collaborative activity of students in the process of cognition and mastery of educational material implies that each student contributes his or her own unique contribution to the process, that knowledge, ideas, ways of activity, and values are exchanged. And it all takes place in a spirit of goodwill and mutual support. Interactive forms increase learning motivation, improve understanding of complicated interpersonal relationships, and aid in the research of individual behavior traits. Traditional means of learning do not allow you to attain a wide range of learning goals as effectively as interactive forms can. There are numerous interactive learning methods available. Each teacher can come up with unique ways to work with the students on their own. When interactive methods are used, the student becomes a

full participant in the perceiving process, and his own experience becomes the primary source of educational knowledge. The teacher does not provide ready-made knowledge, but rather encourages students to conduct their own research. Mutual comprehension, interaction, and mutual enrichment are all benefits of interactive learning.

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